

HYPOGLYCEMICAL EFFECT OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN DIABETES

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Abstract. This article is devoted to diabetes that one of the world's problems and accounts for 60% of endocrine diseases. Treatment of this disease not only with drugs, but also used effectively with medicinal plants that are widely used in everyday life.

Key words: diabetes, blood, sugar, ginger, perennial, common sage, medicinal plant

Currently, in the world health system, diabetes mellitus considered one of the global medical and social problems. The medical and social importance of diabetes explained by the serious complications of the disease, high level of disability and death rate. Therefore, it is important to study the pharmacy-toxicological properties of medicines obtained based on local plants in order to prevent and treat this pathology.

Today, interest in the bean plant is increasing as a representative of leguminous crops, which considered a medicinal plant. The whole world pays special attention to people's health, increases awareness of health secrets, and prefers natural remedies for the treatment of people suffering from diseases of the cardiovascular system, diabetes, rheumatism, and urinary tract diseases. The absolute harmlessness of natural remedies and the sharp increase in the demand for the bean plant in folk medicine was the reason.

In the Resolution of the President of April 10, 2020 "On additional measures for the development of folk medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan", the provision of medical and sanitary assistance to the population. The prevention and treatment

of various, especially chronic diseases has been decided to folk medicine that tested in practice in terms of quality, safety and effectiveness the issue of development.

The main goal of the decision is rapidly integrate the effective methods of folk medicine for the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases into modern medical practice, to further strength the health of citizens, and to establish a system.

Diabetes is the third most common disease after cardiovascular and oncological diseases.

That is why world scientists are focusing on this disease. At the end of the 1950s, diabetes treated only with sulfonamides, iguanids and their analogues. Medicines that taken for a long time have caused several side effects and have toxic effects. Recently, as observed all over the world, the demand for medicinal plants and medicines based on them is increasing in our Republic. This can explained by the fact that herbal medicines well accepted by the human body and have few side effects. It is important to study medicinal plants that grow in our republic and are cultivated in accordance with the climate, which regulate the amount of sugar in the blood, have a number of additional healing properties, and develop new phytopreparations based on them.

Fructose, formed by the breakdown of inulin, can enter all cells without the participation of insulin and can completely replace glucose in metabolic processes. In addition, short fragments of inulin are located in the cell wall, help to transfer glucose to tissue cells, and in this way reduce the amount of sugar in the blood. In addition, since Jerusalem artichoke contains zinc, silicon, potassium and important elements for insulin synthesis, insulin production of the pancreas increases. Prevents the development of diabetic nephropathy, retinopathy and diabetic foot syndrome in patients who regularly consume Jerusalem artichoke.

The current public concern is that through heredity, the consumption of light carbohydrates, refined foods, saturated and Tran's fats, as well as dietary fiber deficiency, overweight and obesity, pathologies of the endocrine system, and long-term, chronic stress one of these diseases is diabetes.

In the modern treatment of diabetes, it prescribed to take dozens of chemical compounds, such as manelin, amaryl, and insulin obtained by synthetic means. All these medicinal substances ensure the easy transfer of sugar from the blood to the cells, in return, the amount of sugar in the blood and urine decreases.

Reducing the amount of sugar in the blood with chemicals causes the pancreas to reduce the production of insulin. Long-term intake of chemicals leads to atrophy of the pancreas. When chemical drugs stopped, blood sugar levels continue to rise. Therefore, in modern medicine, people with diabetes advised to take medicines regularly. Medicines used in folk medicine activate the activity of the pancreas, which aimed at reducing the amount of sugar in the blood by increasing the amount of insulin produced in the body.

Therefore, when diabetes treated with the help of folk medicine methods, it helps to restore the functioning of the pancreas. This allows the patient to stop taking medicine.

All plants growing in our country are medicinal plants.

Studying their composition and using them in the treatment of diseases is one of our main goals. Based on them, it is possible to use phytotherapeutic treatment of diabetes. Among these, one of the most common edible plants is the bean, a representative of the leguminous family.

In conclusion, we can say that many plants growing in our country have medicinal properties. The use of natural remedies in the treatment of diseases is more beneficial for the body. One such disease is diabetes. The use of bean pods as a medicinal plant in the treatment of diabetes helps to be economically and physically healthy.

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